

GS 19 SITE SPHINX	DATE 11/27/79	AREA SE	SQUARE S1-E1	PAGE
 Feature No.	Coordinates:		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Diameter:		Width: 6 cm	Length: 7 cm	Depth: 6 cm vertical / 10 cm slope

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	NONE	Inclusions
1	DARK SAND	BROWNISH	LOOSE	FINE	T	Lm	Gp
					4	Gr	Char
					Small Frag	Do	
					D	Ba	
					D	Al	
					Other		
					T	Lm	Gp
					Gr	Char	
					D	Do	
					Ba		
					Al		
					Other		
					T	Lm	Gp
					Gr	Char	
					Do		
					D	Ba	
					D	Al	
					Other		
					T	Lm	Gp
					Gr	Char	
					D	Do	
					Ba		
					Al		
					Other		

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/	No./	B&W: Roll/	No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan:	Feature Plan:	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Angled, perhaps natural. Excavated previously?
Baraize?